

OBSTETRIC ANTIPHOSPHOLIPID SYNDROME WITH MULTISYSTEM COMORBIDITIES: A COMPLEX CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT:

APLA Syndrome is a thrombotic autoimmune disorder that is often complicated by various vascular problems and needs multidisciplinary management. Presence of various vascular problems such as cerebrovascular, cardiovascular, metabolic, renal and dermatological complications can complicate the problem further. In the present case, we discuss the case of a 36 year old female patient who was diagnosed with obstetric APLA syndrome in association with several comorbidities like cerebrovascular accident (CVA), hypertension, ischemic heart disease (IHD), poorly controlled type 2 diabetes mellitus, chronic kidney disease (CKD) and secondary anemia, and tinea corporis. The patient presented to the outpatient department with complaints of generalized weakness, weakness of upper and lower limbs, slurring of speech, cough, and bilateral lower limb swelling since last 10 days. Physical examination revealed presence of bilateral lower limb edema that was pitting in nature, graded as grade 3 with gradual onset and chronic duration without tenderness. The patient was known case of type 2 diabetes mellitus taking human Mixtard insulin and also known case of CVA for one month along with CKD, hypertension, and tinea corporis.

KEY WORDS:

Obstetric antiphospholipid syndrome; APLA syndrome; cerebrovascular accident; chronic kidney disease; diabetes mellitus; hypertension; anaemia; tinea corporis.

1.INTRODUCTION:

Antiphospholipid syndrome (APS) refers to an autoimmune disease involving the presence of antiphospholipid antibodies and clinical features including thrombosis and/or obstetric manifestations. Obstetric Antiphospholipid Syndrome (OAPS) is one of the key types of antiphospholipid syndromes involving pregnancy loss and other related complications. OAPS involves antibody stimulation of the endothelium, platelet activation, and complement

activation to cause a prothrombotic state [1,2]. APLA patients have a higher incidence of thrombosis, including CVA (cerebrovascular accident), resulting in neurological damage. Thrombotic complications increase if there are other risk factors for cardiovascular disease, such as hypertension, diabetes, and ischemic heart disease. Early diagnosis and necessary preventive measures can lower the morbidity and mortality rates [2,3]. Another comorbidity in autoimmune and vascular disease is chronic kidney disease (CKD). Poor renal function can cause such complications as anemia due to lack of erythropoietin synthesis, chronic inflammation, and problems with iron utilization. Treatment of anemia caused by CKD is challenging [4]. Diabetes mellitus type 2 is usually accompanied by complications such as vascular disease and immune deficiency. Uncontrolled blood glucose levels result in a higher susceptibility of patients to various infections like the skin fungus tinea corporis. In diabetics, dermatophytosis becomes more refractory because of deficiencies in host defenses [5]. Presence of obstetric APLA syndrome along with cerebrovascular accident, hypertension, ischemic heart disease, uncontrolled diabetes mellitus, anemia related to CKD, and tinea corporis is a difficult medical condition to diagnose and treat.

2.CASE PRESENTATION:

This is a 36-year-old patient who complained of general weakness, weakness of the upper and lower limbs, speech disorder, and cough. The patient also had bilateral lower limb swelling for 10 days. The swelling was gradual and chronic without being painful or tender. Bilateral lower limb edema was seen on physical examination. It was of pitting type and grade 3. The patient was a case of obstetric antiphospholipid syndrome (APLA syndrome) with a history of cerebrovascular accident (CVA) for one month. She was also a case of chronic kidney disease (CKD), hypertension, uncontrolled type 2 diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease (IHD), and tinea corporis cruris. This patient was on Human Mixtard insulin for management of type 2 diabetes mellitus. Diet of the patient was found to be variable, while bowel and bladder functions were within the normal limits. There was no previous history of changes in the functional parameters of either of the two organs. Clinical history and physical examination pointed out towards various systemic problems in the nervous, cardiac, metabolic, renal and dermatological systems. Following clinical investigation, it was observed that the patient had obstetric antiphospholipid antibody syndrome along with cerebrovascular accident, hypertension, ischemic heart disease, poorly controlled type 2 diabetes mellitus, chronic renal disease causing anemia, and tinea corporis cruris. Therapy for the patient included a multidisciplinary strategy involving the treatment of the risks of thrombosis associated with APLA syndrome, management of glucose levels, blood pressure, kidney support, management of CKD anemia, and antifungal medications for tinea corporis cruris. Monitoring was conducted on the patient, who improved clinically from the therapy received. Laboratory tests were done in order to assess the patient's hematological status, kidney functions and metabolic abnormalities. There was low hemoglobin (9.7 g/dL) and PCV (28.9%) which indicate presence of anemia. Erythrocytes parameters were found to have TRBC of 3.47 million/ μL and RDW-CV 15%. This indicated morphological changes in the erythrocytes. Increased ESR value (44 mm/hr) indicated presence of some inflammatory processes. Platelet count was high at $402 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$. The patient had increased serum urea value (72 mg/dL) and serum creatinine

(4.8 mg/dL). These values are indicative of poor renal function in chronic kidney disease. Sodium value was reduced (130 mmol/L) which indicated presence of hyponatremia. Urinalysis results show that there was presence of proteinuria with urine protein value of 3+. This indicates the involvement of kidneys in the condition which is chronic kidney disease.

TABLE 1 : LABORATORY FINDINGS OF THE PATIENT

Investigation	Result	Reference Range
Haemoglobin	9.7 gm%	11.9 – 15 gm%
ESR	44 mm/hr	0 – 20 mm/hr
PCV (Hematocrit)	28.9 %	36 – 46 %
TRBC (RBC count)	3.47 million/cumm	3.8 – 4.8 million/cumm
RDW-CV	15 %	11.6 – 14 %
Serum Urea	72 mg/dL	15–45 mg/dL
Serum Creatinine	4.8 mg/dL	0.6–1.1 mg/dL
Sodium	130 mmol/L	135 – 145 mmol/L
Urine Protein	3+	Negative

3.DISCUSSION:

Obstetric antiphospholipid syndrome (OAPS) is an immune-related thrombophilic syndrome defined by the presence of antiphospholipid antibodies associated with pregnancy complications such as recurrent miscarriage, fetal growth retardation, and prematurity. It is caused by the triggering of endothelium, platelets, and inflammation by antibodies, leading to an increased risk of developing thrombotic phenomena [6]. In the case presented here, the patient was suffering from obstetric APLA syndrome complicated by the occurrence of cerebrovascular accident (CVA). Ischemic stroke is one of the major presentations of APS due to the development of thrombus in the arteries. Hypertension, ischemic heart disease, and diabetes mellitus make the risk of vascular events even higher [6]. The patient complained of weakness along with slurred speech, which was a sign of previous cerebrovascular injury. Thrombosis related to APS can occur in both arterial and venous circulation and requires a lifelong management to prevent the recurrence of vascular problems [7]. The patient also had a history of uncontrolled type 2 diabetes mellitus on insulin treatment. Diabetes mellitus leads to dysfunction of the endothelium, aggravation of the development of cardiovascular pathology, and weakening of the immunity. Malregulation of the glucose leads to the development of infections, including dermatophytic infection such as tinea corporis cruris. Laboratory tests revealed that the patient has anemia with low hemoglobin (9.7 gm%), low PCV (28.9%), and low TRBC count (3.47 million/cumm). Tests for renal function indicated high levels of creatinine (4.8 mg/dL) and urea (72 mg/dL), urine protein 3+, which means chronic kidney

disease with the development of proteinuria. Anemia is common in patients with chronic kidney disease because of insufficient production of erythropoietin [8]. Bilateral grade 3 pitting lower limbs edema can occur because of renal impairment, protein loss, and accumulation of fluids. Patients with chronic kidney disease require regular examinations of the renal functions and electrolyte balance [9]. The management of this case entailed a multidisciplinary effort in addressing risk factors of thrombosis, heart disease, diabetes, kidney dysfunction, anemia, and fungal infections. Early diagnosis and customized approaches to management are important for ensuring a better prognosis in patients with multiple conditions.

4.CONCLUSION:

Obstetric antiphospholipid syndrome is a rather complicated autoimmune pathology with a high risk of developing thrombotic and obstetric complications. This case study underlines the problems related to the management of the patient suffering from OAPS accompanied by cerebrovascular accident, hypertension, ischemic heart disease, poorly controlled type 2 diabetes mellitus, chronic kidney disease with secondary anemia, and tinea corporis cruris. Comorbid conditions pose a threat to health due to the increased risk of vascular complications, kidney disorders, anemia, and infectious diseases. The patient's laboratory data revealed the signs of anemia, nephropathy, hyponatremia, and marked proteinuria indicating the need for thorough examination and close monitoring of organ involvement. Management plan encompassing the control of thrombotic risk, cardiovascular disorders, hyperglycemia, kidney disease, correction of anemia, and antifungal therapy is crucial for enhancing the state of health of the patient. Follow-up, adequate education, and treatment adherence are the critical elements in preventing complications among patients with complicated APLA syndrome.

CONSENT

As per international standards or university standards, patient(s) written consent has been collected and preserved by the author(s).

DISCLAIMER (ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE)

Author(s) hereby declares that NO generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, etc.) and text-to-image generators have been used during the writing or editing of this manuscript.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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